

Enhance Learner Creative Thinking Using By Brain Based Learning Strategies

Saloni¹ & Prof. Arun Kumar Kulshrestha²

¹Research Scholar, Department of Pedagogical Sciences, Dayalbagh Educational Institute, Agra (U.P)

²Professor, Department of Pedagogical Sciences, Dayalbagh Educational Institute Agra (U.P)

Corresponding author- Saloni

Email- raghasaloni0000@gmail.com

Abstract

Learning is a lifelong process. All learning is undoubtedly brain-based. Everyone's brain is unique. Brain based learning has been important pedagogy that can be effectively used to enhance creative thinking. A well planned and implemented educational system is crucial for a child holistic development. Brain based approach is required to strength and develop learner innate creative thinking. Brain based learning creates a safe threat, free environment, where meaningful content provide and information appropriately to students (Aziz z-ur- Rehman et.al.,2012). Brain based learning emphasizes on creating a relaxed environment, creative thinking and providing the student with stimulating and innovative experience, challenging techniques of learning which involved all the bodily senses that allowed them to hypothesize, predict, research, investigate, imagine.

Keywords: Brain Based learning strategies, Creative thinking

Introduction:

Learning is always an important part for every organism on earth whether it is any animal or human being. It starts with birth and goes on till the last breath of every creature. At every point everyone tends to learn something from various situations that comes through their way but this learning is not similar for everyone as everyone has individual differences. In different situations, these differences in learning occur according to their prior experiences in life.

Concerning the reason above, the teacher tries to use a learning style. It is brain based method is one of the reading method that helps teachers keep students interested as they think about what they want, what they know and what they have learned. It is a part of the learning by doing teaching method where students move away from what are considered traditional methods of teaching and learning. In this particular methodology the students are given the space to learn by constructing their own learning pace and their own style of understanding a given topic or idea.

Brain Based Learning:

The brain scanning technology has helped researchers to respiration, body temperature, digestion and brain's study the functioning of brain like how the memory, recall, alertness. Then there is the limbic area of brain which emotion, attention, pattern, context, speech, language, regulates fear conditioning and other aspects of emotional thinking, reasoning, speaking, reading, learning, etc. are memory. processed. It has opened the ways to study extensively the biologically alive brain and the

various functions and complex processes involved during the process of learning. The brain based learning is a developing discipline which coalesce the findings of education, neuroscience, psychology, and pedagogy in order to maximize the output of teaching learning process. The understanding of the functioning of brain and its application in the field of education has given rise to the concept of "brain based learning". Brain based learning has emerged as a multidisciplinary approach and has linked neuroscience, pedagogy and the educational psychology. Brain based learning is designed in such a way that the attention, memorization, understanding and meaningfulness are maximized during the learning by encouraging the natural operational principles of the brain. Brain based learning is also known as brain-compatible learning and is based on findings of neurology applied in the field of education to understand how the brain naturally learns the best. It involves designing instruction for learning which promote learning by understanding the functioning and processes of brain. These instruction strategies thus help the brain to Some part of limbic area process and interpret specific learn better. Brain based learning is an extensive approach that applies the findings in education to improve the teaching learning process.

Twelve Brain Based Learning Principles:

Twelve Brain Based Learning Principles were developed by Caine and Caine(2002). The following brain based principles are general theoretical foundation for brain based learning. These principles are simple and neurologically sound.

<https://images.app.goo.gl/xNkqkUEzRah1jFKP>

1. Learning Engages the Entire Physiology-Like the heart, liver, or lungs, the brain is an incredibly complex physiological organ functioning according to physiological rules. The actual wiring of the brain is affected by school and life experiences. Anything that affects our physiological functioning affects our capacity to learn

2. The Brain is social-The brain ceaselessly performs many functions simultaneously. They interact with other brain processes such as health maintenance and the expansion of general social and cultural knowledge.

3. The search for Meaning is innate-The search for meaning (making sense of our experiences) is survival-oriented and basic to the human brain. The brain needs and automatically registers the familiar while simultaneously searching for and responding to novel stimuli. This dual process is taking place every waking moment. The search for meaning cannot be stopped, only channeled and focused.

4. The search for Meaning occurs through "Patterning"-In a way, the brain is both scientist and artist, attempting to discern and understand patterns of its own. Designed to perceive and generate patterns, the brain resists having meaningless patterns imposed on it. When the brain's natural capacity to integrate information is acknowledged and invoked in teaching, vast amounts of initially unrelated or seemingly random information and activities can be presented and assimilated.

5. Emotions are Critical to patterning-What we learn is influenced and organized by emotions and mindsets involving expectancy, personal biases and prejudices, self-esteem and the need for social interaction. Thus, emotions and cognition cannot be separated. Emotions are also crucial to memory because they facilitate the storage and recall of information.

6. Every Brain Simultaneously Perceives and Creates Parts and Wholes-In a healthy person the two hemispheres are inextricably interactive, irrespective of whether a person is dealing with words, mathematics, and music. The value of the two brain doctrine is that it requires educators to acknowledge the brain's separate but simultaneous tendencies for organizing information.

7. Learning involves both Focused Attention and Peripheral Perception-The brain absorbs the information of which it is directly aware and to which it is paying attention. It also directly absorbs the information and signals that lie beyond the immediate focus of attention.

8. Learning always involves Conscious and Unconscious Processes-We learn much more than we ever consciously understand. Most of the signals that we peripherally perceive enter the brain without our awareness and interact at unconscious levels. Having reached the brain, this information emerges in the consciousness with some delay, or it influences motives and decisions.

9. We have two types of Memory: A spatial Memory System and a set of Systems for Rote learning-We have a natural spatial memory system which does not need rehearsal and allows for 'instant memory of experiences. The system is always engaged and is inexhaustible. It is enriched over time as we increase our natural categories and procedures. The system is motivated by novelty. In fact, this is one of the systems that drives the search for meaning.

10. Learning is Developmental -Our native language is learned through multiple interactive experiences involving vocabulary and grammar. It is shaped both by internal processes and by social interaction. That is an example of how specific items are given meaning when embedded in ordinary experiences. Education is enhanced when this type of embedding is adopted.

11. Learning is enhanced by Challenge and Inhibited by Threat-The brain learns optimally when appropriately challenged, but 'down shifts' under perceived threat. In language of phenomenology, we narrow the perceptual field when threatened by becoming less flexible and by reverting to automatic and often more primitive routine behaviors.

12. Each Brain Is Unique -Although we all have the same set of systems, including our senses and basic emotions, they are integrated differently in each and every brain. In addition, because learning actually changes the structure of the brain, the more unique we become.

Creative Thinking :

Creativity is found in every living being to a greater or lesser degree. Development and progress in various fields of life are the result of creativity. Man gets some powers by nature from birth itself, the most prominent of all these powers is creativity. In general terms, creativity is the ability to do something meaningful, innovative and unique, but it will prove to be useful only when the quality of utility is present in this unique thinking. Which proves useful for the society. According to Devdral (1956) - "Creative ability is called that which produces some new things, creations or ideas which are new or which were not known earlier."

Creative abilities are the means that a person uses to express his creative potential. According to Guilford (1959) these abilities are general to some extent and can be used for a variety of tasks. According to Guilford, these abilities together constitute creative thinking. Its main dimensions are originality, flexibility and fluency.

Who does not know the name of Newton today? But very few people know that why he became a scientist? Who doesn't see things falling? But what was the force that created the interest in the falling apple? Once Newton was sitting under a tree when he saw an apple fall from the tree. Here the thought sitting inside him woke up and asked, O apple! Why do you keep falling down instead of going up? What was it then, the great law of gravitation came to us but we should not forget that there was creativity behind it (Gupt, G., 1996).

Classroom strategies based on brain based learning to enhance creative thinking -

1. Use emotional connections.
2. Use a creative model.
3. Use a convergent and divergent thinking.
4. Use a collaborating approach.
5. Use a incubation model.
6. Use brain storming method.
7. Use think pair and share .
8. Use group discussion.

How Brain-Based Learning Impacts Creativity:

Educators must let students learn in teams and use peripheral learning. Teachers structure learning around real problems, encouraging students to also learn in settings outside the classroom and the school building. Man is a social animal, he has to live adjusted in the society. Man is also called a creative animal. Creativity develops in a person by thinking in different ways. Many inventions in the society are based on creativity. For example, when a scientist develops a new technology If someone builds an instrument using iron, he shows his creativity. The development of our society depends on science, therefore, to develop science, a positive attitude towards science requires a creative thinking,

due to which creativity should be given importance and efforts should be made that every person should be creative thinking. There is no suitable environment for the development of creativity in our country, just as a healthy plant needs pure seed as well as suitable soil and climate, similarly for the creative development of the child as well as suitable teaching for the development of science Method, syllabus etc. is necessary (Gulati, S., 2009).

Brain-based learning strategies promote students' creativity. Through these strategies, students get safe, stress-free, and successful learning experiences. The research study reported that brain-based learning is used while teaching in traditional classrooms. Ignores suggestions made by neuro scientific research in research concluded that all teachers should change their traditional classroom to brain-based learning. If the teacher changes the classroom, students' creativity will increase. (Matheev,M.Kallarkl.,T.,2020)

The National Education Policy (2020) has outlined the changing role of teachers, today it is necessary for a teacher to know the students, understand their behavior in the classroom, prepare suitable conditions for their learning, maintain the curiosity of the students, motivate them Provide opportunities for expression and respect experiences. At present, there is a need for such teaching methods which can attract students creative thinking.

Brain-based learning strategies help develop skills and understanding Students' body, mind and brain perform all three functions. Each teacher determines his teaching method according to his personality and according to his understanding. It is a well-known fact based on extensive research that students take interest in education through brain-based learning. It is necessary that the teacher is aware of the effectiveness of brain-based learning strategies and has the knowledge of how and to what extent brain-based learning can be used. The main objective of teaching is that children get maximum learning experiences. To achieve this objective, it is necessary that at the time of teaching some such strategies should be used which are more effective according to the immediate needs of that time, that is, brain-based learning strategies attract the students, thus making classroom teaching effective.

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